

Cooperative Function of Two Active Ears via Interaural Coupling

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Abstract. The left and right ears of some non-mammals can act as a “pressure-gradient receiver” to improve directional sensitivity by virtue of acoustic coupling of the tympanic membranes via the interaural canal (IAC). A seminal study by Roongthumskul et al. (2019) extended this to show that the two active inner ears of a gecko can also effectively synchronize (i.e., each adjusts their self-oscillation frequencies due to coupling). This result is significant because it suggests that the two ears can expend energy to influence one another, with myriad implications for auditory function (e.g., low sound level localization). A subsequent study examining *Anolis* lizards showed that spontaneous and evoked otoacoustic emissions (OAE) are readily measurable in the IAC using an orally placed probe (Bergevin et al., 2020). Further, acoustic modeling of the IAC using known morphology showed that the motion of one eardrum, presumably driven by the ipsilateral inner ear, was sufficient to drive the contralateral eardrum and thereby couple the two (inner) ears. We expand upon those studies by reporting simultaneous SOAE measurements made externally at the left and right meatuses from six anoles. Several general features were considered, including overlap of SOAE spectral magnitudes across ears and vector strength determined from the phase. Half the experiments showed clear magnitude overlap from both ears above 1.5 – 2 kHz but less of a match below. The other lizards exhibited SOAE activity that was not as well-matched between ears. Similar to that reported for geckos, vector strength was often observed to be elevated in regions of overlapping SOAE activity, including about the “valleys” between peaks. Further, vector strengths could show larger maximum values for anole compared to gecko. Individual SOAE peaks were also filtered to extract amplitude (AM) and frequency modulations (FM), from which we performed fluctuation correlation analyses. We found that ipsilateral pairs (i.e., peaks at different frequencies measured from one ear) could show weak AM correlations (usually for nearest neighbors), but no FM correlations were present. However, relatively much stronger AM and FM correlations could be observed for peaks at similar frequencies measured simultaneously across ears – even at the valleys between peaks. Further, correlation delays between ears were not constant (i.e., it did not appear that one ear was uniformly driving the other). Additionally, we examined the effect of external sound stimulation to determine a “trans-IAC” transfer function (i.e., from one probe sealed at the external meatus relative to the other). These exhibited attenuation across the spectrum and phase-gradient delays slightly longer than expected, given the probe separation. These measurements suggest additional delay contributions beyond airborne acoustic propagation (e.g., tympanic motions) and that an emission measured ipsilaterally may contain contributions from both ears. In summary, this study bolsters evidence that the two ears of a lizard may act cooperatively by actively synchronizing via the IAC.

BACKGROUND & MOTIVATIONS

Many organisms exhibit bilateral symmetry (e.g., two eyes, two ears), which has important implications for sensory perception. Auditory processing by the left and right ears provides a basis for binaural sound localization. In particular, interaural cues depend on comparisons between the differences in the level (interaural level differences, ILDs) and timing (interaural time differences, ITDs) of stimuli that reach each ear [1]. This processing occurs neurally in mammals, where the two ears are somewhat isolated across the head. However, in non-mammals, such as lizards, the Eustachian tubes create a direct acoustic pathway between the two tympanic membranes (TyMs), forming an interaural cavity (IAC) where mechanical coupling can occur [2]. Direct IAC coupling forms a “pressure-difference receiver” such that comparisons between sounds received at each ear can form the basis of binaural sound localization [3, 4]. Thus, ILDs and ITDs can arise prior to auditory transduction in the inner ear due to the confluence of sound pressures incident on both sides of the TyM.

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Another key facet of the ear is the generation of spontaneous otoacoustic emissions (SOAE), commonly pointed to as evidence of active force generation in the inner ear that improves its functionality [5]. However, the presence of the IAC complicates the interpretation of measurements. Since the two ears are acoustically coupled via the IAC, the SOAE measured at the external meatus coming from that ipsilateral ear may also contain contributions from the contralateral ear. Further, IAC coupling could influence SOAE generation mechanisms in each ear, perhaps causing the two inner ears to effectively synchronize. Data from lizards lend positive support to SOAE containing bilateral contributions and synchronizing due to coupling [6], including the evidence that SOAE can be detected in the oral cavity of *Anolis* lizards (anoles) [7]. Given the potential implications for sound localization at low sound levels where active force generation would play a role in boosting detection, further study is desirable to understand how the two ears could act cooperatively.

Here, we report on SOAE activity measured simultaneously from both the left and right ears of anoles. We extend the analysis methodology of [6] and also examine correlative behavior in fluctuations in amplitude (AM) and frequency modulations (FM) of filtered SOAE peaks in the temporal domain [8]. Given the high vector strengths reported for gecko SOAE activity between ears [6], we hypothesized that bilateral correlations would be observed, similar to that observed for two peaks at different frequencies measured ipsilaterally. Additionally, correlation analyses can allow for estimates of delays to elucidate how IAC crosstalk manifests (e.g., is one ear dominant in driving the other?).

METHODS

Green anole lizards (*Anolis carolinensis*, $N = 6$) were lightly anesthetized and placed in an acoustic isolation booth. An ER-10C probe (Etymotic Research) was gently coupled to the lizard’s external auditory meatus (Figure 1A) and calibrated with random-phase flat-spectrum noise. A second ER-10C probe was coupled to the contralateral external auditory meatus, and the calibration procedure was repeated. We also performed trans-IAC calibrations for two subjects where stimuli were presented to one ear, and responses were measured at the contralateral ear (Figure 1C). The transfer functions were computed as the contralateral calibration curves relative to the ipsilateral curves, such that the response at the left ear was computed as the response at the left ear to a stimulus presented at the right ear relative to a stimulus presented and recorded at the right ear.

SOAE waveforms were acquired simultaneously from both ears for a duration of 120 seconds at sampling rates of 44.1 kHz. Waveforms were spectrally averaged as 400 buffers of 8192 samples. SOAE peaks were identified as points at least 1 dB above the noise floor, and SOAE “valleys” were identified as the local minima between adjacent peaks (i.e., nearest neighbors; see inset in Figure 1B). We identified bilateral matching peaks as those with center frequencies within 50 Hz of each other. Some peaks < 1 dB were included if there was a matching peak in the contralateral ear’s SOAE spectrum. We computed the phase difference between ears, $\Delta\phi$, from the argument of the ratio of the left ear’s spectrum to the right ear’s spectrum in segments (denoted j) as $\Delta\phi_j(f)$. Then, $\Delta\phi$ was obtained at each frequency, f , by taking the argument of the ensemble average over all segments $\langle e^{i\Delta\phi_j(f)} \rangle$ [6]. The vector strength, V , was computed as $V = |\langle e^{i\Delta\phi_j(f)} \rangle|$ and measures the degree of phase-locking between two signals (from no phase-locking at 0 to perfect phase-locking at 1), serving as an indicator of synchronization between binaural measurements [6].

SOAE peaks were isolated with a recursive exponential filter in the spectral domain [9]. Where possible, filter bandwidths for matching peaks were identical. We evaluated temporal fluctuations in peak envelopes (amplitude modulation, AM) and instantaneous frequencies (frequency modulation, FM; see Figure 4A). We computed interpeak correlations (IPP $_{xc}$) for AM*AM (e.g., dashed line in Figure 4B) or FM*FM (e.g., solid line in Figure 4B) for ipsilateral peaks within an ear (nearest neighbors; IPP $_{xcNN}$) and bilateral matching peaks between ears (IPP $_{xcBI}$). For all subjects, IPP $_{xcBI}$ was computed as the left ear relative to the right (positive lags represent the left ear leading the right). IPP $_{xc}$ were considered statistically significant if the maximum value of the correlation coefficient $|R| > 0.03$ and bootstrapped control values did not exceed this range. The lag at $\max(|R|)$ was designated as the delay (ms).

RESULTS

The trans-IAC transfer function illustrates the effect of external sound stimulation at the contralateral ear (Figure 1C). Specifically, this measure is the closed-field response at one ear relative to the acoustic stimulus being delivered at

FIGURE 1. (A) Schematic of simultaneous bilateral SOAE measurement paradigm in a green anole lizard using an ER-10C probe coupled to each external auditory meatus. Across all panels, responses recorded from the left ear are in blue, and those from the right ear in red. (B) SOAE spectra from an exemplar individual (subject in Figure 2E). The inset identifies matched SOAE peaks (yellow inverted triangles) and valleys (white circles) between 1.05 – 1.65 kHz. Note that there is no symbol at 1.3 kHz because the peak in the right ear corresponds to a valley in the left ear. (C) Trans-IAC transfer function magnitudes, phases, and delays from the same subject as panel B.

the contralateral ear, with the response characteristics of the probes subtracted. A frequency-dependent attenuation of 10 – 25 dB was apparent, as was a variable phase-gradient delay of approximately 150 – 350 μ s between 1 – 8 kHz. The width of an anole head is approximately 1 cm, with an additional 1 cm on each side for the microphone separation relative to the TyM. Thereby, a rough estimate of the sound propagation delay alone would be about 90 μ s. Thus, the observed delays are longer than expected, which may, in part, be attributed to TyM motions [10].

FIGURE 2. Averaged SOAE spectra were measured simultaneously from the left (blue) and right (red) ears of green anole lizards ($N = 6$). Inverted triangles represent matched SOAE peaks between ears. Marker color corresponds to subject ID in Figure 4C.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the degree of spectral overlap between SOAE measured from each ear varied across subjects. Half of the subjects had prominent offsets between ears below approximately 2 kHz, despite minimal differences in calibration curves between 0.5 – 5 kHz. In terms of phase information, unwrapped $\Delta\phi$ were flat at the peaks in the SOAE spectrum (Figure 3A–C middle row), even in subjects with prominent spectral offsets below 2 kHz (e.g., Figure 3A). Vector strength (V) was highest at matched SOAE peaks, with $V > 0.80$ at some frequencies (Figure 3A–C bottom row). Additionally, V could also be elevated at the valleys between peaks. Figure 3D illustrates bilateral spectra measured independently (six minutes between measurements) to demonstrate that synchronized measurements underlie these features. Here, unwrapped $\Delta\phi$ was noisy, and all $V < 0.20$. A two-way ANOVA revealed that while the matched peak frequency did not influence V for bilateral measurements ($F_{1,170} = 2.52, p = 0.115$), SOAE spectral location (i.e., at a peak, valley, or outside of the peak/valley region) was a predictor of vector strength ($F_{2,170} = 21.5, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc comparisons determined that the mean vector strength was statistically significantly different between all three groups ($p < 0.002$ for all three comparisons) and was highest at the SOAE peaks ($V = 0.361$), moderate at the valleys ($V = 0.243$), and lowest outside the peak/valley region ($V = 0.0651$).

FIGURE 3. SOAE spectra (top row), unwrapped $\Delta\phi$ (middle row), and vector strength (bottom row). Panels A, B, and C represent data from three unique subjects (corresponding to panels E, B, and F in Figure 2, respectively). Inverted triangles represent matched peaks where $V > 0.3$. Panel D presents data from the same subject as panel C but with spectra from two different bilateral measurements obtained six minutes apart as a control.

Interpeak correlations for ipsilateral pairs of nearest neighbor peaks and contralateral pairs of matched bilateral peaks are summarized in Table I. While no $IPP_{xcFM_{NN}}$ were observed, weak positive $IPP_{xcAM_{NN}}$ occurred in almost one-fifth of pairs. $IPP_{xcAM_{BI}}$ were more than twice as common as $IPP_{xcFM_{BI}}$; the former were also stronger with longer delays and could be positive or negative, while the latter were exclusively positive. $IPP_{xcAM_{BI}}$ were stronger and had delays an order of a magnitude shorter than $IPP_{xcAM_{NN}}$. Vector strength at the matched peak frequency in correlation with AM R_{BI} ($\rho = 0.511, p < 0.001$) and FM R_{BI} ($\rho = 0.509, p < 0.001$) but was not related to their corresponding delays. Considering only significant IPP_{xcBI} , matched peak frequency did not correlate with AM or FM R_{BI} or $lags_{BI}$ but had a moderate positive correlation with AM $lags_{BI}$ ($\rho = 0.470, p = 0.002$). When evaluating $IPP_{xcAM_{BI}}$ delays as a function of frequency (Figure 4C), it was apparent that the delays were not uniform across the spectrum for most subjects (5/6).

DISCUSSION

SOAE waveforms were recorded simultaneously from both ears of green anole lizards. Each ear had a unique spectral structure, and bilateral SOAE spectra revealed clear overlaps in each subject (Figure 2). While the degree of similarity could vary across subjects, they were accompanied by clear patterns in phase differences and vector strengths associated with SOAE peaks (Figure 3). Additionally, our evaluation of SOAE peak temporal properties revealed that bilateral relationships were more common and often stronger than those within an individual ear, and delays were not consistent across peaks (Figure 4C). These results suggest that the two active ears could work together.

TABLE I. Summary of interpeak correlation properties for $N = 6$ subjects. Positive IPP_{xc} represents the percentage of significant correlations where $R \geq 0.03$. R and lags for significant correlations presented as mean values with standard deviations.

IPP _{xc} Type	Number of Pairs	Method	Significant IPP _{xc}	Positive IPP _{xc}	R	Lag (ms)
NN ^a	98	AM	18.4%	100.0%	0.0517 (0.0296)	1.25 (2.08)
		FM	0.0%	-	-	-
BI ^b	46	AM	82.6%	89.5%	0.184 (0.177)	0.178 (0.687)
		FM	37.0%	100.0%	0.0756 (0.0364)	0.0867 (0.414)

^a NN = nearest neighbor peak ipsilateral correlations.

^b BI = matched peak bilateral correlations.

FIGURE 4. (A) Segments of envelopes (dotted pale lines) and instantaneous frequencies (solid bright lines) extracted from the left (blue) and right (red) ears of subject in Figure 2A at 2.7 kHz. (B) Using the same data as panel A, IPP_{xcAMBI} (black dashed line) and IPP_{xcFMBI} (black solid line) between ears with respective control (dashed grey and solid grey lines). Shaded region identifies boundary of ± 0.03 . (C) Interpeak AM delays relative to matched peak frequencies. Only SOAE peaks that matched across ears and had IPP_{xcAMBI} $|R| > 0.03$ were included. Marker colors correspond to subjects in Figure 2 and sizes indicate the strength of $|R|$ (between 0.04 – 0.6). Dashed horizontal line represents 0 ms lag (i.e., no delay between the envelopes).

Bilateral interpeak correlations obtained between two ears at matched peak frequencies were more common and stronger than those measured ipsilaterally within a given ear. The presence of positive and negative delays supports that the observed bilateral cross-correlations are not the result of one dominant ear primarily driving the other. If one ear was always synchronized to the contralateral ear, we would see solely positive or negative delays for a given subject. Thus, it seems that IAC crosstalk can occur independently in frequency-dependent channels. Such results are consistent with predictions from modeling data that indicate that both ears contribute to the sensitivity of a system [6]. Bilateral synchronization has important implications for sound localization, presumably refining interpretations of ILDs and ITDs, and could give rise to the strong directionality observed in the lizard’s peripheral auditory system (e.g., [11, 12]).

Vector strength between the two ears was higher near SOAE peaks, even at the valleys between peaks. This was particularly prominent in ears that had elevated “baseline” activity, such that the SOAE peaks appeared to sit atop a hump in the noise floor (e.g., Figure 3C). Likewise, while not extensively evaluated here, IPP_{xcBI} could be observed in the valleys between peaks, albeit with lower R_{BI} values than the peaks. Such properties suggest that these elevated noise floors are not merely noise but a feature of the anole’s SOAE spectrum, consistent with the broad baseline emissions reported in geckos [13]. This feature may reflect coupling between the clusters of oscillators that have been proposed to underlie the generation of SOAE peaks in lizards [14]. While not addressed here, we can also measure evoked emissions (e.g., SFOAE and DPOAE) where the stimulus was delivered to the contralateral ear. It was observed that these stimuli could readily influence an ipsilateral SOAE. These show attenuation consistent with the trans-IAC transfer function and both ears contributing to the measured emissions.

Our evaluation of the trans-IAC (Figure 1C) provides evidence that the observed offsets between some SOAE spectra (e.g., Figure 2B, C, or E) cannot be attributed to errors in calibration or one ear behaving differently from the other. Anecdotal evidence suggests that small changes in the coupling of the probe to the external meatus can have a large effect on the SOAE. For example, gently pushing or pulling the probe after sealing it to the side of the head can

dramatically alter the observed SOAE activity, somewhat similar to static pressure changes (e.g., [15]). Past results from geckos indicate that varying static pressure in the ear canal can affect the vector strength of bilateral SOAE [6]. Thus, manipulating the probe coupling could change the effective impedance of the reverse pathway of the middle ear (i.e., what load is upon the inner ear “looking back outwards”), perhaps by changing the tension on the TyM.

The coupling of the two probes could affect how the two ears synchronize via the IAC since the TyMs act as important boundary conditions. Comparisons of SOAE spectra in a given ear obtained before and after coupling the contralateral ear are qualitatively similar. However, subtle shifts in peaks and changes to the noise floor may reflect the bilateral coupling changing the synchronization of the ears. Further measurements are needed to clarify how the measurement method may influence IAC coupling and bilateral synchronization. In particular, simultaneous OAE and vibrometry measurements (e.g., via laser Doppler vibrometry [4, 11]) can help us better understand how probe coupling relates to TyM motion and how this affects bilateral SOAE activity.

CONCLUSIONS

We observed stronger interpeak correlations for peaks at similar frequencies measured across the two ears, as opposed to two at different frequencies measured ipsilaterally. This observation suggests that IAC coupling can lead to stronger synchronized behavior of SOAE-generative elements across ears rather than generators inside an individual inner ear. Whether it be SOAE or evoked emissions, we must consider that an OAE measured ipsilaterally at one ear in animals with IAC-coupling, such as lizards, could reflect a mixture of activity from both ears. Or, at least, activity primarily generated by the ipsilateral inner ear is actively shaped by the contralateral ear.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Manuela, Nowotny:] Is it possible to vanish somehow the SOAEs, like pharmacologically or something else, and to see how it comes in again and if it is coupled because that it is telling something about the more dominant ear?

[Rebecca, Whiley:] Yes, [SOAEs] can be manipulated pharmacologically, though we don't personally do that work [Note: See Long & Tubis Hear Res 1988 for an example of SOAE reduction with aspirin consumption]. One of things we look at to manipulate their activity is temperature. My poster at ARO earlier this year was looking at how the correlations between adjacent peaks, so ipsilateral peaks, could fluctuate as we increase and decrease the lizard's body temperature. One thing we've also found is just manipulating the probe coupling can have an effect on the spectrum that we get, so we have to be very careful to make sure that we're keeping stable experiment conditions.

[Robert, Fettiplace:] What do you think the basis of the tuning is?

[Rebecca, Whiley:] My understanding is that there is some degree of electrical resonance at the lower frequencies but there has to be some degree of hair bundle mechanics that are contributing to it as well.

[Robert, Fettiplace:] These are free hair bundles. What is the length change?

[Rebecca, Whiley:] I can give a rough illustration here, but I don't have the exact numbers. [Note: Slide with adaptation of Figure 3 from Negandhi et al. Canad Acoust 2018 was shown to illustrate bundle height change (increasing from apex to base) along the papilla.]

[Robert, Fettiplace:] The interesting thing is you have nine peaks. What's generating these peaks? Is it a row of hair cells?

[Rebecca, Whiley:] My hypothesis is that it's related to the clustering of adjacent hair cells, so the nearest neighbours.

[Robert, Fettiplace:] Well, there have to be discrete rows, so there's nine rows?

[Rebecca, Whiley:] I don't think it has to necessarily be just in a row. It could be happening both laterally and longitudinally.

[Robert, Fettiplace:] No, it has to be discrete because you're going down into a valley in between them. It has to be nine rows, or perhaps 18 rows.

[Christopher, Bergevin:] I think the answer to your second question is we don't know, and I think Becky [Whiley] conveyed one idea for that heuristically. The first question would be that the bundles vary, there are about 20 rows where they're bidirectionally oriented and it varies anywhere from 40–50 microns tall for the bundles at the low-frequency end, down to about 2–3 microns [at the high-frequency end]. But I might be a little off. Geoff [Manley] is nodding his head no, so I might be a bit off in those numbers. [Note: According to Manley & Gallo JASA 1997, bundle heights (i.e., height of the tallest stereovilli) in *Anolis sagrei* vary from 20–3 microns. According to Negandhi et al. Canad Acoust 2018, a similar range is found for *Anolis carolinensis*.]

[Jont, Allen:] Just look at the picture: you can see that the lengths are changing, the width is changing. I mean it's not very analytical, but it's pretty clear what's going on just by looking at the picture. Right or not?

[Geoff, Manley:] I hadn't actually indicated any intention to ask a question, but let me just say to Jont [Allen] that, if you look at the papilla and say it's narrow at one end and wide at the other, that does not necessarily correlate with frequency. The height of the bundle is different and it will vary between about 10 and 30 [microns] at the low frequency end. But if you look at geckos, you see a change in the width but it's actually the opposite of what you would expect. So, you need to know the numbers and you also need to know where the tonotopicity is.